
RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Benefits of Extensive Reading for Moroccan EFL University Students: Insights from a Case Study

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| ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of an extensive reading program (Cycle Licence d'Education) on the vocabulary knowledge, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills of 88 Moroccan English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students. Over 14 weeks, with 120-minute sessions weekly, participants engaged with texts from various fields such as history, philosophy, sociology, psychology, education, politics, religion, and science. Using a quantitative research design, pre- and post-assessments were conducted to measure the outcomes of the Extensive Reading Module. Results showed a significant improvement in vocabulary, with two-thirds of the participants (66%) reporting considerable progress in both vocabulary acquisition and its practical application. The program also affected positively reading comprehension, as 93% of students felt confident in their ability to read and understand complex texts. Furthermore, 84% of students acknowledged that the program significantly enhanced their critical thinking abilities after engaging with literary and academic materials. These findings provide valuable insights for EFL/ESL educators and curriculum designers, showing how extensive programs can help build language skills and promote critical engagement with academic and literary texts.

| KEYWORDS

Extensive reading, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, critical thinking, digital resources

| ARTICLE INFORMATION

ACCEPTED: 01 January 2025

PUBLISHED: 13 February 2025

DOI: 10.32996/jeltal.2025.7.1.11

1. Introduction

Extensive reading (ER) is an approach to language learning that prioritizes reading large quantities of material for pleasure, enjoyment, and general understanding, rather than detailed analysis. For decades, this method has become popular in educational settings due to its ability to engage learners with diverse texts and genres and develop a love for reading. Day and Bamford (1998) and Bamford and Day (2004) argue that extensive reading can improve language skills and encourage a lifelong interest in reading. Unlike intensive reading (IR), which involves studying shorter texts closely, extensive reading allows students to come across vocabulary and grammatical structures in a natural setting, that facilitates learning and retention. According to Jacob and Farrel (2012), learners who read frequently and in large quantities grow to love the reading experience. The fundamental tenet of ER is that students should read and study what interests them at their own speed and convenience.

Extensive reading has further shown its merits in promoting vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills of learners (Koda, 2005; Grabe, 1988; Horst, 2005; Yamamoto, 2011). To begin with, it is common knowledge that building one's vocabulary is crucial to learning a language since it lays the foundation for effective communication and comprehension. According to Grabe (1988), "fluent readers need a massive amount of receptive

vocabulary that is rapidly, accurately, and automatically accessed and lack of such a vocabulary knowledge may be the greatest single impediment of fluent reading by ESL students" (p. 63). This suggests that ESL (English as a Second Language) students need to work on developing their vocabulary knowledge if they want to become fluent readers. One method to achieve this is via

extensive reading programs, which provide learners of English with opportunities to develop their vocabulary through repeated encountering of individual words (Horst, 2005). In addition, Hiebert and Kamil (2005) contended that extensive reading significantly enhances vocabulary breadth and depth by providing learners with repeated exposure to new words in various contexts. Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Mayo and Hanzeli (2018) found that students engaged in extensive reading demonstrated significant vocabulary gains compared to their counterparts who participated in more traditional reading activities, illustrating the method's efficacy in fostering language growth.

Reading comprehension is another critical area influenced by extensive reading. Findings from a study by Hafiz and Tudor (1989) indicate that learners who engage in extensive reading show marked improvements in their ability to understand and analyze texts. This improvement stems from the regular practice of encountering diverse genres and formats, which equip learners with strategies for decoding and making inferences.

In today's information age, critical thinking skills are paramount. It is evident that extensive reading plays a crucial role in developing critical thinking skills by exposing learners to diverse narratives and perspectives. In other words, extensive reading encourages students to engage with texts critically as they develop their ability to assess arguments, recognize biases, and express their opinions. For instance, in a study by Husna (2017), it was found that students stated that extensive reading improved not only their reading language skills but also developed their critical thinking skills.

Based on the above, it seems that the benefits of extensive reading are limitless. With the integration of extensive reading as a module (course) in the undergraduate English curriculum (Licence d'Education), there is limited research about the effectiveness of extensive reading on enhancing vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills of Moroccan university students. In addition, the specific challenges Moroccan learners face, including varying levels of English proficiency and access to reading materials and digital content, have not been addressed in the literature. This gap highlights the need for a research study examining the impact of extensive reading on Moroccan EFL students, providing valuable data to inform curriculum developers and practitioners in higher education.

2. Theoretical framework

This research paper is based on two theoretical models of extensive reading and vocabulary development, namely the transactional theory of reading (and writing) and the input hypothesis. To begin with, the transactional theory of reading and writing, a theory proposed by Louise Rosenblatt (1978), highlights the dynamic relationship between the reader and the text, arguing that meaning is created by the reader's experiences and the context in which they read.

According to Rosenblatt's view, readers who practice extensive reading tend to engage with texts in a way that is meaningful to them, which promotes a deeper understanding of and connection with the reading material. Research also indicates that students are more likely to stay motivated and involved when they select texts that align with their interests, enhancing their overall reading comprehension (Guthrie et al., 1999; Schiefele et al., 2016).

Another theory that frames this research paper is the Input Hypothesis developed by Krashen (1982). According to this hypothesis, language acquisition occurs most effectively when learners are exposed to comprehensible input which is slightly above their current proficiency level. This implies that students, who interact with a variety of texts that present new vocabulary in meaningful contexts, are more likely to learn and retain new words.

3. Literature Review

The impact of extensive reading on EFL/ESL students' language skills and proficiency has been the subject of several studies (Liu & Zhang, 2018; Husna, 2019; Ateek, 2021; Endris, 2018; Suk, 2017). As mentioned above, extensive reading refers to a method of reading instruction that offers a wide variety of reading materials for learners to engage with on their own. In extensive reading classes, students are required to read extensively for general meaning, information, or pleasure (Day, 2018).

Most studies on extensive reading in L2 settings have reported that it leads to gains in reading abilities and vocabulary acquisition (Beglar et al., 2012; Webb & Chang, 2015; Grabe, 2009). For instance, in an English as a second language (ESL) setting, Horst (2005; as cited in Suk, 2016) investigated 21 adult immigrant ESL students' vocabulary growth in a six-week extensive reading program, using an innovative method to assess students' vocabulary growth. Results of pre- and post-tests showed that the participants made a significant mean gain of 17 words from the measure of the 1001-2000 frequency band words and off-list words. In addition, Peregoy and Boyle state that "familiarity with text types facilitates reading comprehension" (2000, p. 240; as cited in Celik, 2019). This suggests that repeated exposure to new words results in improved learning. As learners recognize new words when they come across them in texts, their comprehension will lead to the acquisition of new vocabulary.

Moreover, Al-Nafisah (2015) conducted research to examine the impact of an extensive reading program on the reading comprehension of Saudi EFL university students. A total of 54 students from King Saud University were randomly selected and divided into an experimental and a control group, with 27 students in each. Data was gathered through pre-tests and post-tests over a three-month period. The results revealed that the experimental group had superior performance in reading comprehension compared to the control group.

The development of critical thinking skills in ESL/EFL reading classes has become the subject of various studies. Some studies have examined the influence of extensive reading on critical thinking, or how the amount of reading can influence critical thinking development. For instance, Eftekhary & Kalayeh (2014) studied how extensive reading can help Iranian ESL/EFL students improve their critical thinking at Rasht Azad University. They found that the integration of critical thinking activities in reading classes was an important way to help Iranian students solve problems. The study showed that students with good critical thinking skills understood the reading material better, and that better reading comprehension also helped improve their critical thinking skills.

As noted from the previous research on the effects of extensive reading on reading comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, and critical thinking, the majority of studies indicated positive merits of ER on these skills in ESL/EFL contexts. However, common limitations include: (a) the role of technology or digital devices in extensive reading classes was not assessed; (b) most EFL studies focused on examining the effects of extensive reading either on reading comprehension and vocabulary knowledge, or on critical thinking skills; while studies that explore the effects of extensive reading on all three—vocabulary knowledge, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills are relatively scarce; (c) despite the incorporation of extensive reading into the curriculum for English major students (Cycle Licence d'Education), only a few studies exist in the literature regarding the gains of extensive reading in Moroccan EFL contexts.

Therefore, the following objectives guided this study:

1. Evaluate the extent to which extensive reading enhances the vocabulary development and improve reading comprehension skills among Moroccan EFL university students.
2. Assess how extensive reading contributes to the development of critical thinking skills of Moroccan EFL university students.
3. Explore the role of technology and digital resources in extensive reading classes for EFL learners.

4. Method

4.1. Participants

The participants in this study were 88 Moroccan EFL learners studying at a public education institution in Morocco. The participants were second year undergraduate students (Semester 3) majoring in English studies (Licence d'Education). The majority of these participants (92%) were classified as having low intermediate language proficiency

(based on their grades in Semester 1, Semester 2, and Semester 3). All participants were between 18-22 years of age ($M = 19,35$; $SD = ,817$). Their L1 was Moroccan Arabic and approximately two-thirds (65.9%) of these participants reported having 4 to 7 years of English language learning experience (please see Table 1).

Participants were informed that the main goal of the study was to improve the course content and assess its outcomes. Before the study was conducted, all students reported that they had never participated in an extensive reading program and that some of them occasionally read novels or short stories for pleasure in Arabic, English, or French.

4.2. The Reading Materials

The reading materials were part of the Extensive Reading Module (course). The course aimed to enhance students' reading comprehension skills and strategies, introduce them to the methods of critical reading and text analysis, and expose them to a range of knowledge by exploring representative texts from various disciplines and fields. The syllabus covered various reading materials, from academic texts to literary works. Students were expected to complete the weekly assigned readings before each class. Each class session consisted of two hours dedicated to discussion and reflection on the texts.

The following is a list of texts that were part of the Extensive Reading Module:

- A Modest Proposal by Jonathan Swift
- History: A Worthwhile Academic Discipline by Gelien Matthews
- Allegory of the Cave by Plato
- The Id, Ego, and Superego by Freud
- Science Has Spoiled my Supper by Philip Wylie
- Women, Family, and Private Property by Friedrich Engels
- Academic Freedom and Student Riots by Sidney Hook

4.3. Assessment Tools and Data Collection

The impact of the extensive reading program on students' language skills and proficiency was evaluated using a structured questionnaire, which was divided into six sections. The first section aimed to collect data regarding participants' demographics such as age, gender, English proficiency level, and years of experience with the English language.

The second section focused on students' perceptions of their vocabulary development. It included three subsections (pre- and post-test measures, and use of new vocabulary) with three multiple-choice questions.

The third section aimed to examine how the extensive reading program contributed to improving students' reading comprehension skills. This section had three subsections (pre- and post-test measures, and ability to understand complex texts) and three multiple-choice questions.

The fourth section aimed to assess the role of using digital tools and resources in extensive reading. This section consisted of two subsections (use of digital tools, and impact of digital tools) with one yes/no question and one multiple-choice question.

The fifth section aimed to examine the influence of the extensive reading program on students' critical thinking skills. It included two subsections (perceived improvement in critical thinking, and integration of critical thinking) with two multiple-choice questions.

The sixth and final section aimed to evaluate students' overall experience with the extensive reading program and find out if they had any recommendations or suggestions to improve the course. This section included two subsections (overall experience, and recommendations) with one multiple-choice question and one open-ended question. For further details, please refer to the appendix.

The data collection process occurred during two-hour extensive reading sessions in December 2023¹. Students were informed about the voluntary nature of the study one week before it began and instructed on how to complete the questionnaire. All participants expressed their willingness and consent to complete the questionnaire.

5. Results

5.1. Demographic Information

The following table (Table 1) provides the demographics of participants

Table 1. Participants' Demographic Information

Participants	N (88)	% (100)
Age: Between 18 – 22 years-old	88	100
Gender	12	13,6
• Male	76	86,4
• Female		
English Language Proficiency	7	8
• Beginner	81	92
• Low Intermediate		
Experience with English Language	0	0
• Less than 1 year	30	34,1
• 1-3 years	58	65,9
• 4-7 years		

¹ It should be noted that, since September 2024, both the name and syllabus of the Module "Extensive Reading" have been changed to "Critical Reading".

5.2. Assessment of Vocabulary Skills

5.2.1. Pre- Assessment Measures

Participants were asked to rate their vocabulary skills before engaging in the extensive reading program using a five-point Likert scale (very poor, poor, average, good, excellent). The results showed (see Figure 1) that the majority of participants (78.4%) reported their vocabulary skills as "poor" or "average" prior to engaging in the extensive reading program.

Figure 1. Pre-Assessment of Vocabulary Skills

5.2.2. Post Assessment Measures

After the program (course) ended, participants were asked to rate their vocabulary knowledge following their engagement in extensive reading using a five-point Likert scale (very poor, poor, average, good, excellent). According to the results (see Figure 2), the majority of the participants (72%) reported their vocabulary skills as "good" or "excellent" after engaging in the extensive reading. This suggests that the extensive reading program had a positive effect on EFL students' vocabulary knowledge.

Figure 2. Post-Assessment of Vocabulary Skills

5.2.3. Use of New Vocabulary

Next, participants were asked to indicate the extent to which they use the vocabulary acquired through the extensive reading program in their daily English communication. They responded using a five-point Likert scale (not at all, rarely, occasionally, frequently, always). The results revealed that most participants (81%) reported "occasionally" or "frequently" using the new vocabulary learned from extensive reading in their everyday English communication.

Figure 3. Participants Perceptions of Their Use of New Vocabulary

5.3. Assessment of Reading Comprehension Skills

5.3.1. Pre- Assessment Measures

Similar to the vocabulary assessment measures, participants were asked to evaluate their reading comprehension skills prior to participating in the extensive reading program using a five-point Likert scale (very poor, poor, average, good, excellent). The results (see Figure 4) showed that most participants (73%) rated their comprehension skills as “poor” or “average” before starting the extensive reading program.

Figure 4. Pre- Assessment of Reading Comprehension Skills

5.3.2. Post- Assessment Measures

After the program ended, students were asked to assess their reading comprehension skills using a five-point Likert scale (very poor, poor, average, good, excellent). The results (see Figure 5) indicated that the majority of participants (81.2%) reported their comprehension skills as “good” or “excellent” after participating in the extensive reading program. These findings suggest that extensive reading has a positive impact on EFL students’ reading comprehension skills.

Figure 5. Post-Assessment of Reading Comprehension Skills

5.3.3. Ability to Understand Complex Texts

After completing the pre- and post-assessment measures for comprehension skills, participants were asked to rate their confidence in understanding complex English texts using a four-point Likert scale (very confident, moderately confident, slightly confident, not confident). The results (see Figure 6) revealed that the majority of participants (93.2%) reported being "slightly confident" and moderately confident" in their ability to understand complex English texts.

Figure 6. Participants Perceptions of their Ability to Understand Complex Texts

5.4. Assessment of critical thinking skills

5.4.1. Perceived Improvement in Critical Thinking

To determine whether the extensive reading program improved students' critical thinking skills, participants were asked to rate their skills based on a five-point Likert scale (no improvement, little improvement, moderate improvement, substantial improvement, significant improvement). The results showed that more than two-thirds of the participants (69.3%) reported "moderate" to "substantial" improvement in their critical thinking skills.

Figure 7. Participants Perceptions of the Improvement in their Critical Thinking Skills

5.4.2. Integration of Critical Thinking Skills

In addition, participants were asked to indicate the extent to which extensive reading helped them develop critical thinking skills. The results (see Figure 8) revealed that the majority of the participants (84.1%) reported that the extensive reading program “moderately” or “very much” helped them apply critical thinking skills when engaging with materials not directly related to the Extensive Reading Module.

Figure 8. Participants Perceptions of the Integration of Critical Thinking while Engaging with Other Materials

5.5. Assessment of the role of digital tools and resources

5.5.1. Use of Digital Tools

Beyond assessing vocabulary knowledge, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills, this study also explored the role of digital tools and resources in extensive reading classes. The results indicated that the majority of participants (95.5%) reported using digital tools and resources, such as online libraries and language learning apps, to support their extensive reading.

Figure 9. Use of Digital Tools

5.5.2. Impact of Digital Tools

Participants were then asked to indicate the extent to which they believed digital tools and resources had improved their language skills in the Extensive Reading Module. Approximately 60.2% of the participants reported that digital tools had “very much” or “extremely” contributed to their improvement.

Figure 10. Participants Perceptions of the Impact of Digital Tools

5.6. Overall experience and recommendation

5.6.1. Overall Experience

At the end of the questionnaire, students were asked to rate their satisfaction and overall experience with the extensive reading program. Roughly 75% of participants reported being “satisfied” to “very satisfied” with the reading materials used in the program for developing vocabulary, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills.

5.6.2. Recommendations

Participants then were invited to provide recommendations or suggestions to enhance the effectiveness of extensive reading programs for vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills among English major students. The following is a summary of the recommendations and suggestions provided by the participants.

Table 2. Participants' Recommendations for Improving the Effectiveness of Extensive Reading Programs

1.	Read texts in class to enhance engagement with the topics covered.
2.	Add a session dedicated to learning and reflecting on new vocabulary.
3.	Use short texts.
4.	Allow students to choose their own texts to boost motivation.
5.	Incorporate short stories from a variety of topics and fields.

6.	Focus on reading literature to improve vocabulary and critical thinking.
7.	Include more philosophical books or articles to improve critical thinking.
8.	Allocate more hours to extensive reading sessions, with the freedom to choose essays.
9.	Integrate mini-games and debates.
10.	Use Videos and pictures as the module is highly engaging.

6. Discussion

This research study used a convenience sampling of 88 undergraduate English major students enrolled in a public higher institution in the northwest of Morocco. The primary objective was to assess the extent to which extensive reading enhances students' vocabulary knowledge, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills. Additionally, this study explored the role of digital tools and resources in extensive reading classes. The participants, aged between 18 and 22 years, were predominantly female (86.4% female; 13.6% male) and were enrolled in the Extensive Reading Module (Semester 3) as part of their bachelor's degree requirements in education (English major). Most participants possessed a low intermediate level of English proficiency level and had no prior experience with extensive reading programs.

The extensive reading syllabus covered a list of academic and literary texts, such as "Science Has Spoiled My Supper" by Philip Wylie, "Allegory of the Cave" by Plato, and "A Modest Proposal" by Jonathan Swift. For over 14 weeks, students had to read weekly assigned reading materials at home and reflect on them in class. At the end of the course, participants completed a questionnaire designed to assess their perceptions of the program's effectiveness. This questionnaire incorporated pre- and post- assessment measures of vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking.

The findings of this research showed that the extensive reading program positively impacted EFL students' vocabulary development. Most participants reported using newly learned vocabulary in their spoken English. These results align with previous studies that suggest that ER promotes vocabulary acquisition as learners are exposed to abundant input, leading to incidental and incremental vocabulary learning over time (Peglar, Hunt, & Kite, 2012; Webb & Chang, 2015). Research in EFL settings also highlight that applying newly acquired vocabulary in spoken language contexts is crucial for vocabulary retention and language development. These findings imply that EFL educators should integrate classroom activities that facilitate the practical application of newly acquired vocabulary, particularly for struggling learners.

Not only ER had proved its merits in vocabulary learning but also had been associated with enhanced reading comprehension skills. According to the results, most of the surveyed students reported a positive influence on their reading comprehension and critical thinking abilities. Other research studies also highlight the relationship between extensive reading and improved reading comprehension in EFL instruction (Tamrackitkun, 2010). This implies that by reading a wide range of texts, learners are exposed to diverse linguistic structures, styles, and content, thereby deepening their understanding. For instance, Huffman (2014) demonstrated that participants engaged in ER significantly outperformed those in intensive reading groups.

Furthermore, studies conducted in EFL contexts have increasingly acknowledged the role of ER in fostering critical thinking skills among language learners (e.g., Husna, 2019). In this respect, researchers have claimed that extensive reading helps EFL learners to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize texts by exposing them to a broad range of viewpoints, ideas, and perspectives in texts. This exposure supports the development of critical thinking skills. The findings of this study suggest that incorporating tasks that focus on analysis, evaluation, and synthesis within extensive reading programs should further enhance these skills.

Moreover, this study found that students reported relying heavily on digital tools and resources to support their language learning in ER classes. This suggests that EFL learners generally perceive online extensive reading positively. A recent case study by Tabata-Sandom (2023) showed that an online extensive reading project positively influenced participants' motivation, reading habits, and linguistic abilities. Other research studies have identified several advantages of online extensive reading, such as faster reading speed, increased motivation, and easier access to digital resources (Sun, 2021; Zhou & Day, 2021; Bui & Macalister, 2021).

The majority of the surveyed students expressed satisfaction with the course content of the Extensive Reading Module. Most of them believed that the reading materials helped them develop their vocabulary, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills. However, participants offered several recommendations for improving the course. These suggestions included incorporating in-class reading sessions to enhance engagement with the topics, allowing students to choose their own texts to boost motivation, and integrating mini-games and debates. Participants believed that implementing these recommendations should enhance engagement and interest in future extensive reading programs for English learners (see Table 2 for further details).

7. Conclusions and limitations

To conclude, this research paper highlights the multifaceted benefits of extensive reading in EFL contexts, particularly among Moroccan English major students. The findings demonstrated that ER fosters vocabulary knowledge, and enhances reading comprehension and critical thinking skills. Additionally, the use of digital tools and resources has proven to be fundamental and valuable in extensive reading classes.

This study further emphasizes the importance of designing extensive reading programs that align with students' needs. Recommendations such as integrating in-class reading sessions, offering students the freedom to choose their own texts, and integrating interactive activities such as debates and games, are essential to boost students' motivation and interest in the program. These insights are particularly relevant for practitioners and curriculum designers who seek to optimize the effectiveness of extensive reading modules in EFL settings.

While this research paper provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The reliance on self-report questionnaires and the absence of a control group may introduce bias, as participants' subjective perceptions or tendencies to overestimate their language abilities and engagement in ER could affect the validity of the results. Future EFL studies should address these limitations by employing other research methods such as randomized sampling or longitudinal designs, that could offer deeper insights into the effects of extensive reading on language development and critical thinking.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Publisher's Note: All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers.

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Appendix

Assessment of the Effects of Extensive Reading on Vocabulary Development, Reading Comprehension, and Critical thinking

Objective: The following questionnaire aims to assess the effectiveness of extensive reading in developing the vocabulary, reading comprehension, and critical thinking skills of Moroccan English university students. Participation in this questionnaire is voluntary. All responses will be analyzed and used only for academic purposes. Taking the time to complete this questionnaire will be highly appreciated and acknowledged.

Section 1: Demographics

1.1. Personal Information:

- Age:
- Gender:
 - Male
 - Female

1.2. Current English Proficiency Level:

- Beginner
- Intermediate

1.3. Years of English Learning:

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-7 years

Section 2: Vocabulary Assessment

2.1. Pre-Assessment:

- How would you rate your vocabulary skills before engaging in extensive reading?
 - Very poor
 - Poor
 - Average
 - Good

- Excellent

2.2. Post-Assessment:

- How would you rate your vocabulary skills now, after engaging in extensive reading?
- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Excellent

2.3. Use of New Vocabulary

- To what extent do you use new vocabulary learned through extensive reading in your everyday English communication?
- Not at all
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Frequently
- Always

Section 3: Reading Comprehension Skills

3.1. Pre-Assessment:

- How would you rate your reading comprehension skills before engaging in extensive reading?
- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Excellent

3.2. Post-Assessment:

- How would you rate your reading comprehension skills now, after engaging in extensive reading?
- Very Poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Excellent

3.3. Ability to Understand Complex Texts:

- How confident are you in your ability to understand complex texts in English after engaging in extensive reading?
- Not confident at all
- Slightly confident
- Moderately confident
- Very confident

Section 4: Critical Thinking

4.1. Perceived improvement in Critical Thinking:

- How would you rate the improvement in your critical thinking skills since starting extensive reading?
- No improvement
- Little improvement
- Moderate improvement

- Substantial improvement
- Significant improvement

4.2. Integration of Critical Thinking

- To what extent do you think extensive reading has helped you develop critical thinking skills while engaging with other materials?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Moderately
 - Very much
 - Extremely

Section 5: Role of Digital Tools and Resources

5.1. Use of Digital Tools:

- Do you use digital tools or resources to support you extensive reading? (e.g., e-books, online libraries, language learning apps)
 - Yes
 - No

5.2. Impact of Digital Tools

- To what extent do you believe the use of digital tools has improved your language skills in extensive reading?
 - Not at all
 - Slightly
 - Moderately
 - Very much
 - Extremely

Section 6: Overall Experience and Recommendation

6.1. Overall Experience:

- How satisfied are you with your overall experience of using reading for vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking?
 - Very dissatisfied
 - Dissatisfied
 - Neutral
 - Satisfied
 - Very satisfied

6.2. Recommendations:

- Do you have any recommendations for improving the effectiveness of extensive reading programs for vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and critical thinking among English learners?